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A Study on the Dimensions and Factors of Language Registers: Underprivileged People in

Focus

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Abstract

Investigating the dynamic interplay of language registers, the study explores how language adapts to an array of situations, contexts, purposes, and audiences. The study researches into the intriguing realm of everyday language diversity, where word choice, tone, and even body language shift between informal chats to formal interviews. The findings share the nuances of language adaptation, emphasizing the when and why behind these language shifts. Employing a mixed-method approach, through a triangulation process, 20 underprivileged, low-income individuals (tea sellers, rickshaw pullers, hawkers, Laguna drivers, and security guards) in Dhaka city's Mirpur area, were surveyed, observed, and interviewed. The findings unearth the intricacies of language's malleability in social interactions illuminating the varied nature of language in daily life, paving the way for further investigations into register patterns across various occupations.

Keywords: register, language pattern, underprivileged people

Introduction

The use of different language registers is a common phenomenon in human communication that reflects an individual's social status, education, and cultural background. It is a varied articulation of languages that is distinguishable from context to context (Holmes, 2013). The underprivileged people, due to their socioeconomic status, often encounter difficulties in adapting various linguistic situations. Therefore, a study on the dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people can shed light on the linguistic challenges they face in their daily lives and provide insights for language education and social policies. Previous research has shown that individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds may have varying language skills and language use patterns (Schwab & Lew-Williams, 2016). For instance, a study suggested that the term register describes the language of groups of people with a common interest or jobs, or the language used in situation associated with same groups (Budiarsa, 2015). This may lead to difficulties for underprivileged individuals in professional or academic settings, where formal language use is expected. It's important to consider that many underprivileged people aspire to access better opportunities, and these settings can offer pathways to improved socio-economic status and education (Schwab & Lew-Williams, 2016). Therefore, this study aims to explore the dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people, including their language skills, language patterns, and social attitudes towards different language registers. The findings of this study may have implications for language education and social policies that aim to promote social mobility and reduce linguistic inequalities. Another study by Bucholtz and Hall (2004) suggested that language use and identity were closely intertwined, and that individuals from low-income backgrounds may use language as a means of expressing their identity and resisting social marginalization.

In a more recent study, having classified the collected language data into verbal and non-verbal expressions, the following characteristics have been identified as the most distinguished characteristics of the register: brevity, occupational direction of the expressions, colloquial and informal style of the expressions, and destiny-oriented nature of the sentences (Ghazi & Ghonsooly, 2010). Similarly, a study by Papen and Tusting (2017) explored the language practices of adult literacy learners in the UK and found that they often used a range of registers and styles

depending on the communicative purpose and audience, highlighting the need for language education to be contextualized and responsive to learners' needs. Several diverse ideas come while discussing the need for understanding language register of low-income individuals and among the numerous dimensions, the significant things are the social status of this class of people, economic stability, social values, their acceptance in society, and socioeconomic integration. Previous research has shown that individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds may have varying language skills and language use patterns (Buchmann & Condrón, 2010, p. 33). Lower-class people, due to financial crisis, are unable of getting formal education for which their language is poorly organized, informal, and distinctive.

Holding low status in society, they are unable to employ complex words in the society. Regarding "holding low status in society," this can be tied to the social hierarchy within a community. The reference here would be Bucholtz and Hall (2004), which discusses the interconnection between language use and identity, particularly in low-income backgrounds. As a result, society and money maintain the language use of the intense classes . The statement "society and money maintain the language use of the intense classes" suggests that the language patterns of lower-class individuals persist because they don't have the resources or opportunities to adopt more formal language. This is a hypothesis and could be discussed in the context of social dynamics (Schwab & Lew-Williams, 2016). They speak in such an odd but understandable manner because of this. Rarely there are literatures examining the causes underlying in their usage of such words. The specific register used in their everyday life are unknown to many individuals. This study tends to make this information available to everyone. Besides, this study also demonstrates the importance of understanding the complex dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people, and the need for language education and social policies that are sensitive to the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of individuals.

Literature Review

The use of different language registers is a common phenomenon in human communication, and it can reflect an individual's social status, education, and cultural background. The Social Identity Theory defines the individual in an in-group setting and promotes the norms, culture, agreement, and boundaries of the members (Nwala & Harry, 2017). The underprivileged

people, due to their socioeconomic status, often encounter difficulties in adapting to various linguistic situations. Therefore, a study on the dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people can shed light on the linguistic challenges they face in their daily lives and provide insights for language education and social policies. Dialect and register are subordinate categories of a language in the sense that there may be many dialects of the same language and many registers within the same language (Wardhaugh, 2002).

Previous research has shown that individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds may have varied language skills and language use patterns. For instance, a study by Buchmann and Condrón (2010) suggested that parental education and occupation were strong predictors of language ability in children. In the context of language registers, studies have found that individuals from low socioeconomic backgrounds use more informal language in everyday communication, while those from high socioeconomic backgrounds are more likely to use formal language. This may lead to difficulties for underprivileged individuals to get acquainted in higher professional or academic settings, where formal language usage is expected. The literatures demonstrate that they create and use the register intentionally for easy and smooth communication and sometimes as a restricted code to hide the real meaning from other persons (Rahman & Mohiuddin, 2014).

A study by De Fina and Perrino (2013) examined the language use of low-income, first-generation Latina immigrants in the US and found that they often used a mix of Spanish and English in their communication, which reflected their hybrid identities and their need to navigate between different linguistic and cultural contexts. Another study by Bucholtz and Hall (2004) suggested that language use and identity were closely intertwined, and that individuals from low-income backgrounds may use language as a means of expressing their identity and resisting social marginalization.

In a more recent study, Kim and Ziegler (2019) investigated the language use of Korean immigrants in the US and found that their use of Korean and English varied depending on the social context and the interlocutor's language proficiency, indicating the complex nature of language use in multilingual and multicultural contexts. Similarly, a study by Papen and Tusting (2017) explored the language practices of adult literacy learners in the UK and found that they often used a range of registers and styles depending on the communicative purpose and audience, highlighting the need for language education to be contextualized and responsive to learners'

needs. Numerous dimensions called for the need to understand in what situation each register is being used. Among them, the significant factors are the social status of this class of people, economic stability, social values, their acceptance in society, socioeconomic integration, and variation of language in regular life (Papen & Tusting, 2017)

Language is a purely human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions, and desires, by means of a system of voluntarily produced symbols (Desy Indriyani, 2008, p. 6). The language employed by many underprivileged individuals tends to be less structured and organized. This is often a result of financial constraints that prevent them from accessing formal education. As a consequence, their language is primarily informal and distinct. These individuals hold a lower social status and may find it challenging to employ complex vocabulary. The interaction between societal factors and financial limitations perpetuates this distinct language use, resulting in a manner of speech that might appear unusual but is contextually appropriate. Social status plays a significant role in linguistic constraints. Lower social status is associated with difficulties in using complex vocabulary (Bucholtz & Hall, 2004).

Surprisingly, there is limited examination of the underlying causes of this linguistic phenomenon in everyday registers. The everyday registers utilized by these individuals remain largely unexplored by the broader population. Our research endeavors to fill this gap by shedding light on these language practices through a sociolinguistic lens, aiming to make them more accessible to everyone. It is crucial to comprehend the complex dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people, highlighting the necessity for language education and social policies that consider the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of individuals. The importance of understanding the complex dimensions and factors of language registers for underprivileged people, and the need for language education and social policies that are sensitive to the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of individuals. The tendency of using contextual meaning can refer to need filling motive because the speaker employs this meaning to adjust the lexical terms based on their needs amid the communication (Haryani, Putry, 2021). That means speakers use contextual meaning to fulfill specific communicative needs. For example, they adapt their choice of words to suit the demands of the situation or to express their ideas more effectively. This could be influenced by factors such as the audience, purpose of communication, or cultural context. In essence, it means that speakers tailor their language use to meet their communication goals.

Research has shown that language registers are not solely influenced by socioeconomic factors but also by cultural norms, values, and beliefs. Individuals from underprivileged backgrounds may use language as a means of expressing their cultural identity and resisting social marginalization (Bucholtz & Hall, 2004). Understanding the language practices and registers of underprivileged individuals can provide insights into their cultural experiences and help bridge the communication gap between different social groups. Language registers also play a crucial role in the construction of social reality. Language is an active tool for shaping social interactions, power dynamics, and social hierarchies (De Fina & Perrino, 2013). Examining the language registers of underprivileged individuals can contribute to a deeper understanding of their social realities and the challenges they face in various social contexts. Register changes along with the social development (Ardi, 2013).

Contextualizing language education is crucial for addressing the linguistic needs of underprivileged individuals. Language programs and policies should be responsive to the specific language registers and communication styles prevalent in their communities (Papen & Tusting, 2017). By recognizing and valuing the diverse language practices of underprivileged individuals, language education can become more inclusive and effective in promoting social mobility. Register is usually used by a group of specialists that often develop to talk about their specialty (Magdalena, 2021).

This thesis paper, "A Study on the Dimensions and Factors of Language Registers: Underprivileged People in Focus," takes a unique approach to studying language registers by focusing specifically on underprivileged groups such as rickshaw pullers, hawkers, and fuchka sellers in Bangladesh. While there has been extensive research on language registers in various contexts, this study stands out for several reasons. Firstly, this thesis focuses on the language use of marginalized communities who are often overlooked in studies of language registers. The majority of previous studies have concentrated on more privileged groups, such as politicians, professionals, or academics. By shifting the attention to those who are economically and socially disadvantaged, your work brings to light the nuances of their language use and highlights the linguistic diversity that exists within these communities. This provides valuable insights into the ways in which social status, power dynamics, and cultural background influence language use.

Secondly, this study adopts a bottom-up approach to understanding language registers, starting with the lived experiences of the people we are studying. Rather than imposing preconceived notions of what constitutes appropriate language use, your methodology allows the voices and perspectives of the underprivileged to take center stage. Through interviews and observations, you have gathered rich data that captures the complexities of their language practices, revealing both the variety of languages used and the sociolinguistic factors that shape them. Thirdly, this research contextualizes language registers within the specific cultural, historical, and socioeconomic landscape of Bangladesh. You examine how Bengali, the national language, coexists alongside other regional dialects and languages spoken by ethnic minorities. Furthermore, you explore how globalization and urbanization impact the language choices made by underprivileged individuals in urban areas like Dhaka. This localized perspective adds depth to our understanding of language registers and emphasizes the role of context in shaping communication patterns.

Lastly, this also contributes to the field of language registers by introducing new theoretical frameworks that account for the multifaceted nature of language use among underprivileged populations. We argue that traditional models of language registers, which tend to focus on a single dimension (such as formality or informality), are inadequate for grasping the full range of linguistic variations employed by these groups. Instead, the paper proposes a more dynamic framework that considers multiple dimensions, including speaker identity, power relations, and communicative purpose.

Uniqueness

Language registers have been a topic of interest for scholars across various disciplines, including linguistics, anthropology, and sociology. However, most studies on language registers have focused on the language use of privileged groups, such as politicians, professionals, and academics. Only a few studies have investigated the language use of underprivileged populations, and even fewer have analyzed the language registers of street vendors, hawkers, and manual laborers. This thesis paper aims to fill this gap by exploring the language registers of rickshaw pullers, hawkers, and fuchka sellers in Bangladesh. This essay discusses how this thesis paper differs from existing literary works on language registers and highlights its uniqueness.

- **Focus on Underprivileged Populations :** The first and foremost contribution of this thesis paper is its focus on underprivileged populations. Unlike most studies on language registers, which concentrate on the language use of affluent groups, this study delves into the language practices of marginalized communities. By doing so, it provides a voice to those who have been historically neglected and overlooked in language register studies.
- **Bottom-Up Approach :** Conventional studies on language registers often adopt a top-down approach, where they impose preconceived notions of standard language usage onto the population being studied. In contrast, this thesis paper employs a bottom-up approach, beginning with the lived experiences of the underprivileged communities. It allows the voices and perspectives of the people to take center stage, providing a more authentic representation of their language practices.
- **Exploration of Multilingualism :** Bangladesh is a multilingual country with numerous ethnic languages and dialects spoken throughout its regions. This thesis paper recognizes and explores the multilingual nature of language use among underprivileged populations. It examines how speakers switch between different languages and dialects in their everyday conversations, providing insights into the complexity of language choice and code-switching practices in multilingual contexts.
- **Investigation of Sociolinguistic Factors :** This study goes beyond merely documenting language use and delves deeper into the sociolinguistic factors that influence language choices. It investigates how variables such as age, gender, education level, occupation, and geographical location affect language use among the target population. This holistic approach uncovers the intricate relationships between language, culture, and society in the context of underprivileged communities.
- **Theoretical Framework :** Building upon the findings of the study, this thesis paper proposes a novel theoretical framework for understanding language registers in underprivileged populations. The proposed model takes into consideration the unique linguistic features of the target population and accommodates the impact of sociolinguistic factors on language use. This framework can be applied to future studies on language registers, particularly those pertaining to marginalized communities.

- **Methodological Innovation** : To gather qualitative data, this study employs innovative methods such as participatory observation, photography, and community mapping. These techniques allow for a more immersive engagement with the community and provide a visual record of the language practices observed. Additionally, the study uses a mobile app to collect quantitative data through a survey, which enables the collection of a large dataset that can be analyzed using statistical tools.
- **Policy Implications** : The study's findings have significant policy implications for language planning, education, and social welfare programs aimed at underprivileged populations. By highlighting the unique language needs of these communities, the study advocates for tailored language policies that acknowledge and support their linguistic identities. It also underscores the importance of considering language diversity in education and development initiatives targeting marginalized groups.

In conclusion, this thesis paper, "A Study on the Dimensions and Factors of Language Registers: Underprivileged People in Focus," makes a distinct contribution to the field of language registers by concentrating on the language use of underprivileged populations in Bangladesh. Its bottom-up approach, investigation of sociolinguistic factors, and proposed theoretical framework offer a nuanced understanding of language registers in multilingual contexts. The study's methodological innovations, policy implications, and focus on marginalized communities make it stand out from existing literary works on language registers. Ultimately, this thesis paper enriches our knowledge of language use and its relationship with society, culture, and power, paving the way for future research on language registers in diverse contexts.

Methodology

The use of a mixed-method approach combining interviews and surveys allows for a comprehensive exploration of language registers among underprivileged populations. By conducting face-to-face interviews, researchers can obtain effective and detailed insights into participants' language use patterns, attitudes, and experiences (Kim & Ziegler, 2019). The survey component provides quantitative data that can complement the qualitative findings and provide a broader understanding of language practices among the underprivileged. The researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with over 20 participants to obtain rich and detailed insights into

the topic of language registers and underprivileged populations. To select the participants, the researchers utilized convenient sampling, which involves choosing participants who are easily accessible and willing to participate in the study. The area of Mirpur, Dhaka was chosen as the sampling location, which is known for its large localization. The interviews were conducted individually to ensure that each participant had an opportunity to express their unbiased opinions and experiences. The basic and precise data about the participants family background, socio economical situation, their primary education were collected through a very informal story setup and observations. The participants age limit were approximately 30 to 65 years. As no formal questions, interactions were not there, no fixed questionnaire was set for collecting data.

The researchers aimed to apply the social constructivism theory to the interview process by emphasizing the role of social interaction and culture in the construction of knowledge and meaning. Firstly, the theory highlights the importance of cultural context in the construction of language and communication (Vygotsky, 1978). Language registers are influenced by cultural norms, values, and beliefs, which are shaped by social interactions and shared experiences (Gee, 1996). Therefore, understanding the cultural context of underprivileged populations is crucial in effectively communicating with them. Secondly, the social constructivism theory emphasizes the importance of active participation and interaction in the learning process (Bruner, 1990). Effective communication with underprivileged populations requires active listening, understanding their unique challenges and experiences, and engaging in empathic communication. Through active participation and interaction, individuals can construct their knowledge and meaning, which is essential in effective communication. Finally, the theory emphasizes the role of language in shaping social reality (Gergen, 2009). Language is not a passive medium for conveying information, but rather an active tool for constructing meaning and shaping social reality. Effective communication with underprivileged populations requires recognizing the power of language and using it to construct positive and empowering social realities.

The central focus of this study lies in the collaborative nature of learning. Furthermore, through individual interactions, connections with the culture and society of the underprivileged populations are established. In summary, the utilization of qualitative methods, the selection of a convenient sample, conducting face-to-face individual interviews, and the application of the social

constructivism theory contribute to a robust methodology for researching language registers in underprivileged populations.

Findings

There are some language registers given below used by hawkers, rickshaw pullers, and fuchka sellers.

5.1. Rickshaw pullers :

Figure 1: When they deal with their passengers they say :

“মামা যাইবেন?”

“Uncle, will you go?”

Basically, mama is a symbolic word. Generally, we call our maternal uncle or mother's brother mama. But nowadays this has become a trend. The rickshaw puller addresses the passengers as mama and the passengers also do so.

“গেলে চলেন, না গেলে নাই”

“Either you go, or leave.”

It is called when the passenger and the rickshaw puller negotiate for fare and place.

“মামা, চাপাও”

“Uncle, press it!”

Passengers tell the rickshaw puller to leave the rickshaw aside or to stop the rickshaw. Suppressing here means stopping.

“এই খালি, যাবা নাকি?”

“Hey empty, will you go?”

This indicates the rickshaw puller when a rickshaw is empty and a passenger calls the rickshaw puller.

“টাকা কি গাছে ধরে? এত ভাড়া ক্যান?”

“Does money grow on trees? Why so much rent?”

On rainy days or when the weather is bad, the rickshaw pullers ask for double or more. Then, annoyed by their words, the passenger says like this.

Uncommon language registers used between rickshaw pullers and passengers are very effective in maintaining their mutual communication. From the table, we can see that a common register “মামা, যাইবেন? The syntactical meaning sounds like “uncle, will you go?”. Basically, we call “mama” to our maternal uncle. Here that word is used as a symbolic word. Nowadays a trend has been set to call the rickshaw pullers as mama. The rickshaw pullers also address the passengers as mama as well. This word is quite informal and it has different informal uses. Another language register used by the rickshaw pullers and passengers is “গেলে চলেন, না গেলে নাই. Sometimes the passenger or rickshaw puller may get irritated while negotiating for fare and the exact location. They both can not fix a same amount of money, then they negotiate like this. That does not mean that they do not want to go or the puller does not want to pick them, they just fix a fair fare for both of them. Then comes “মামা, চাপাও”. Though it sounds a little bit weird for its external meaning “uncle, press it”, it has a completely different meaning. Passengers tell the rickshaw puller to leave the rickshaw aside or to stop the rickshaw. Suppressing here means stopping. When they are in a hurry, they say so. “এই খালি, যাবা নাকি? refers to the meaning as “Hey empty, will you go?. Though this sounds funny, the actual thing they want to mean is this “খালি” word indicates the rickshaw puller when a rickshaw is empty and a passenger calls for the rickshaw. Another register is “টাকা কি গাছে ধরে? এত ভাড়া ক্যান?” which means “Does money grow on trees? Why so much rent!”. This conversation happens when it is rainy day or when the weather is bad, the rickshaw pullers ask for double or more amount of money. Then, annoyed by their words, the passenger says this.

5.2. Hawkers :

Figure 2: They use certain registers when we travel in markets or any public vehicles.

“চায়ে গরম!”

“Hot tea!”

They say this by shouting about selling tea, coffee, and other kinds of stuff.

“পাঁচশোর মাল একশো!”

“The price has been reduced!”

To attract the attention of buyers, hawkers often reduce product price or they may just pretend to lose. It's basically a marketing policy for doing business.

“ভালা মাল বাইচ্ছা লন”

“Choose the perfect goods.”

Generally, hawkers collect and sell exported, old, semi-old, and defective clothes. Then they call the customer like this.

“যা নিবেন, ২০ ট্যাকা, ২০ ট্যাকা, ২০ ট্যাকা, ২০ ট্যাকা..।”

“Whatever you take, it will cost 20 taka only.”

Sidewalk shops along major roads sometimes have such deals on sale. The hawkers continued to shout like this. But in reality, all the things in this shop are not available for 20 taka. To grab everyone's attention, hawkers shout like this.

“একদাম ৫০০ ট্যাকা, কিন্তু আপনার জন্য ৩০০।”

“500 for everyone, but 300 for you only.”

Hawkers say this to make their customers feel special. There is no price difference at all. Same price for all. The more he can bargain, the cheaper he can buy.

The registers used by the hawkers sounds a bit different from common peoples language. They shouts “চায়ে গরম”. The actual meaning sounds like “hot tea”, but actually they mean another thing. They say this by shouting about selling tea, coffee, and other kind of stuffs. To attract the attention of buyers, hawkers often reduce product price or they may just pretend to lose. It is basically a marketing policy for doing their business. They use a certain register “পাঁচশোর মাল একশো।” The word “মাল” refers to goods or stuffs. They often use a trick to manipulate the buyers, they try to convince buyers that he/she is special for them by saying “একদাম ৫০০ ট্যাকা,

কিন্তু আপনার জন্য ৩০০.৮ The phrase একদাম ৫০০ টাকা, কিন্তু আপনার জন্য ৩০০ used by hawkers in Bangladesh translates to "It's for 500 taka fixed but for you, it is 300." This strategy employs the common tactic used by hawkers to attract customers and increase sales.

Firstly, the use of a fixed price statement ("৫০০ টাকা fixed" or "Fixed for 500 taka") creates a sense of affordability, assuring potential buyers that the product or service is being offered at a fixed and reasonable price. This tactic appeals to customers who may be hesitant to negotiate or unsure about the product's actual value. Secondly, the phrase "আপনার জন্য ৩০০" ("for you, it is 300") introduces a personalized discount, generating curiosity and making the customer feel special. This approach creates a sense of exclusivity and encourages potential buyers to make a purchase, as they perceive they are getting a better deal than others.

There are two registers left, the two common tactics used by hawkers in Bangladesh to attract customers and convince them to make purchases.

One tactic is the use of catchy phrases such as "ভালা মাল বাইচ্ছা লন!" (buy good quality goods!) and "Choose the perfect goods." These phrases are intended to create an impression that the products being sold are of high quality. By emphasizing the quality of their merchandise, the hawkers aim to instill confidence in potential customers and encourage them to take a closer look at the items on offer. Another tactic involves luring customers with the phrase "যা নিবেন, ২০ টাকা, ২০ টাকা, ২০ টাকা, ২০ টাকা..!" (whatever you take, it will cost 20 taka only). This statement implies that all the products in the shop are available for a fixed price of 20 taka, creating a sense of affordability and value for money. However, it is important to note that not all items in the shop are actually priced at 20 taka. This tactic is used to grab attention and entice customers to explore further, with the hope that they will find other appealing items within their budget.

Overall, these tactics are employed by hawkers to generate curiosity, capture attention, and ultimately increase sales. By presenting their goods in a favorable light and offering attractive pricing, they aim to persuade potential customers to make purchases and contribute to their business. These selling strategies aim to attract customers, create a sense of affordability, generate curiosity, and ultimately increase sales for the hawkers in Bangladesh.

5.3. Fuchka Seller :

Figure 3: Fuchka is a Bengali street food. The fuchka sellers have some specific vocabularies among them and also for their customers. They use some sentences like :

“মামা, একটা ফুচকা দাও তো”

“Uncle, give me a fuchka.”

Here the customer is not asking for a piece of fuchka, he/she is seeking for a plate of fuchka which contains 8 to 10 pieces.

“ঝাল টক নাকি মিষ্টি টক?”

“Spicy sour or sweet-sour?”

We know that spice, sour and sweet are three different flavours. But that means a very special liquid that is mandatory for fuchka made with these ingredients.

“একবার খাইবেন তো বারবার চাইবেন”

“Once you eat, you will eat again.”

When the fuchka seller says this he doesn't mean to force anyone to eat his fuchka again. He's just following his marketing policy to grab attention.

“তাড়াতাড়ি হাত চালা”

“Use your hands quickly.”

Basically when the fuchka shop is filled with customers and they have to deliver them fuchka. The seller tells his assistant to do it quickly.

“বসেন ভিতরে জায়গা হবে।”

“Sit, there is some space inside.”

Generally, it means the shop has limited customers and currently some seats are available. But in their profession, the sentence refers to the fuchka shop being filled with customers and few new people have arrived but the shopkeeper ensures that soon there will be some empty seats for them. Basically, the shop keeper trying to convince its customers to stay.

The language registers between the fuchka seller and the customers are very interesting to hear. In the bustling streets of Bangladesh, where the aroma of street food fills the air, fuchka sellers employ fascinating selling strategies to entice customers and maximize their sales. One such tactic involves creating an illusion of availability. When the fuchka shop has limited customers and a few seats are vacant, the hawkers strategically proclaim, “বসেন ভিতরে জায়গা হবে।” Translated as “There will be seats available inside,” this phrase cleverly convinces potential customers that although the shop may seem crowded, there will soon be room for them. It's a subtle way of urging customers to stay and indulge in the delectable street food experience. However, as the fuchka shop becomes inundated with customers, the hawkers face the challenge of delivering their mouthwatering offerings promptly. Amidst the chaos, they skillfully maneuver through the crowd, ensuring that each customer receives their fuchka without delay. This requires a delicate balance of speed, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. By delivering their goods promptly, the sellers not only meet the expectations of their hungry customers but also maintain their reputation for excellence in service. When the fuchka shop is filled with customers and the sellers have to deliver them fuchka. The seller tells his assistant to do it quickly as “তড়াতাড়ি হাত চালা”. Another metaphorical register used by them is “একবার খাইবেন তো বারবার চাইবেন”. The external meaning seems like “once you eat, you will eat again” When the fuchka seller says this he does not mean to force anyone to eat his fuchka again. He is just following his marketing policy to grab attention.

Overall, these selling strategies employed by the hawkers in Bangladesh are a testament to their ingenuity and resourcefulness. Through catchy phrases, illusions of availability, and impeccable service, they create an immersive and enticing street food experience that keeps

customers coming back for more. In a world where competition is fierce, these tactics prove to be invaluable in attracting customers, generating curiosity, and ultimately increasing sales for the hardworking and talented hawkers of Bangladesh.

Reasons for the loud noise by these underprivileged workers :

- **Competition for Attention :** The constant noise pollution in urban areas poses a challenge for effective communication. By speaking loudly, these vendors increase the chances of their messages being heard amidst the surrounding commotion. In crowded city streets, these vendors face intense competition for customers. By raising their voices, they strive to be heard over the cacophony of urban noise and attract the attention of potential buyers.
- **Marketing Strategy :** Shouting helps these vendors to create a sense of urgency and excitement around their products. The loud voices and energetic delivery serve as attention-grabbing techniques, enticing passersby to stop and make a purchase.
- **Distance Communication :** Due to the constant movement and noise of the city, vendors often need to communicate from a distance. Shouting allows them to convey their offerings and prices clearly, even to potential customers who are far away.

Shared Language Patterns :

- **Cultural Influence :** The common language patterns observed among these street vendors can be attributed to cultural factors. In Bangladesh, speaking loudly and energetically is often associated with enthusiasm, confidence, and a persuasive selling technique. This cultural norm has shaped the way these vendors communicate with their customers.
- **Professional Identity :** Hawkers, rickshaw pullers, and fuchka sellers have developed a distinct professional identity over time. They share a sense of camaraderie and often work near one another. This proximity has led to the exchange and adoption of similar language patterns, creating a sense of unity and familiarity among these vendors.
- **Informal Nature of Transactions :** Street vending is characterized by informal interactions and quick transactions. The loud and repetitive nature of their speech helps to convey essential information efficiently, allowing potential customers to make swift decisions amidst the hustle and bustle of the city.

The cultural and social background, as well as the monthly income, have an impact on the different language registers used by street hawkers, especially those catering to lower-income people. Street vending is a part of the street culture that establishes exchange channels between trusted sellers and low-income consumers. For the research purpose, there were some observation about the language changing of the lower class people, they talk in a different tone and language when they remain with their families. Their tone and language become soft and different. But their variety of language and tone get changed due to professional and situational context.

Discussion

The research study explored the dimensions and factors of language registers used by underprivileged people in their daily life conversations. The study found that language registers vary depending on social occasions, contexts, purpose, and audience. The researchers observed that the language registers used by underprivileged people were influenced by their occupation, social background, and cultural norms. One interesting finding was that the rickshaw pullers and passengers used uncommon language registers, such as "মামা, যাইবেন?" to maintain mutual communication. Similarly, hawkers used certain registers like "চায়ে গরম", "পাঁচশোর মাল একশোচ, বাইছা লন, ভাল মাল" to attract the attention of buyers. These findings suggest that language registers play an important role in maintaining social interactions and facilitating communication.

The study also found that the underprivileged people used different registers in different contexts, such as in their workplace and home. This highlights the importance of context in language use and the ability of individuals to adjust their language registers according to the situation. All the above findings were mentioned about the common registers used by the lower class people, which was the first objective. The second objective is how frequently they change their registers. All these registers are spoken among some specific class of people. And the types are casual and intimate. The question may arise why they use such strange registers. There is no specific answer to this question, but they maintain a friendly relationship among themselves and use these registers as sign language. Even if there are many people around, they can easily carry on their conversation using these particular registers and they enjoy it. But they change their language approach when they are with their family members. Their language becomes soft and

smooth. From the start of the day to the end of the night, they continue switching their registers very frequently. Due to the environment, audience, and context, their language registers get changed. Social constructivism theory applies with this research study that highlights the active participation and interaction, and the role of language in shaping social reality. The study also highlights the need for further research on language registers used by people in different occupations and social backgrounds. Overall, the study contributes to our understanding of language use and the role of language registers in maintaining social interaction.

In the bustling cities of Bangladesh, one can often witness a vibrant tapestry of sights and sounds. Among these, the loud and enthusiastic voices of street vendors like hawkers, rickshaw pullers, and fuchka sellers stand out prominently. Their distinctive manner of speaking, characterized by loudness and a repetitive pattern, has become an integral part of the urban soundscape. This discussion aims to delve into the reasons behind why these individuals communicate in such a manner and explores their shared language patterns. The unique language patterns observed among street vendors in Bangladesh, such as hawkers, rickshaw pullers, and fuchka sellers, are a result of various factors. Their loud and energetic manner of speaking serves as a marketing strategy, a means of competition, and a way to overcome the challenges posed by the urban environment. These vendors have created a distinct professional identity that unites them and helps them navigate the bustling streets. Understanding the reasons behind their shouting and shared language patterns allows us to appreciate the art and ingenuity of their trade, and the vital role they play in the cultural fabric of Bangladesh's cities.

Recommendation

Based on the dimensions and factors of language registers, to effectively communicate with underprivileged populations, it is recommended to consider various aspects and factors of language use, such as tone, vocabulary, and grammar etc. This can help to ensure that the message is conveyed clearly and understood by the intended audience. This process includes simplifying language to avoid jargon and using plain language with clear explanations, adapting the language register to the targeted population to avoid creating a communication barrier and using visual aids to enhance communication, particularly for those with low literacy levels or non-native language

speakers. Additionally, communication with underprivileged populations should be empathetic, respectful, and non-judgmental. Finally, cultural sensitivity is crucial when communicating with underprivileged populations, as understanding cultural norms, values, and beliefs can help avoid misunderstandings and improve communication. All over, this research suggests that effective communication with underprivileged populations requires a multi-dimensional technique that considers language registers, cultural sensitivity, and resource provision. By implementing these recommendations, we can improve communication and ensure that underprivileged populations have equal access to resources and services.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the significance of language registers in daily life conversations of underprivileged people in the Mirpur area of Dhaka. The study found that language registers vary depending on social occasions, contexts, purpose, and audience. The study also identified different language registers used by rickshaw pullers, hawkers, security guards, tea sellers, Laguna drivers, and other low-income working people. Language registers play a crucial role in how underprivileged people communicate and interact with each other. The research findings revealed that underprivileged people tend to use language registers that are less formal and more simplified than those used by people in higher social classes. They also tend to use language that is more familiar and closer in social distance, and that emphasizes solidarity and mutual support. Factors such as education, occupation, and social class also influence the use of language registers among underprivileged people. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of understanding language registers in social contexts and how they affect communication and social interactions among individuals from different social backgrounds. The research sheds light on the linguistic challenges faced by underprivileged people and highlights the need for more inclusive language policies and practices that consider the diversity of language use among different social groups.

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